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EFFECT OF DISLOCATION AND HONEYCOMB HEIGHT ON COMPRESSION PERFORMANCE OF TANDEM HONEYCOMB

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1. Background

Nomex honeycombs have specific high stiffness and strength, which are most commonly used core material in aerospace and transport application. This paper focus on the compressive property of the tandem honeycombs, which has more design and performance compared to single honeycomb.

The following are typical application of tandem honeycomb:

Figure 1 Application as an energy absorber on a train

Figure 2 Application of thick honeycomb core restoration

2. Experimental results

Group C

Group CW

Interface layer

Group CWC

Top view of dislocation

Group	Layer	Dislocation	Interface layer	Core height
C	1	no	no	20
CW	2	no	yes	10+10
CWC	2	yes	yes	10+10

The dimension of the specimen is 50mm (L) \times 50mm (W) \times 20mm (H). All the material property and geometry of the specimens are the same.

The face sheets of the specimens are metal aluminium plates with a nominal thickness of 1mm.

2. Experimental results

Test setup of a honeycomb core under flatwise compression.

Three types of specimens were subjected to a Flatwise compression test in accordance with the requirements of the ASTM-C365. The static tests were performed on an MTS loading machine with a loading rate of 0.5mm/min, this provides quasi-static loading conditions. The event was recorded at 5 Hz.

2. Experimental results

Deformation process of the honeycomb core under a flatwise compressive load

Series (a) is the deformation process of group C, (b) is group CW, and (c) is CWC. The left shows the initial state of specimen, the middle shows the cell wall starts to fold as the compressive displacement was raised to 0.4 mm just before collapsing, and the right shows the destructive state of specimen.

Particularly, the dislocation assembly group CWC could be observed that the obvious honeycomb mutual invasion phenomenon at the two-layer honeycomb interface during experiment.

2. Experimental results

Experimental results of C

Experimental results of CW

Experimental results of CWC

Group	Young's modulus (MPa)	Collapse stress(MPa)
C	110	1.93
CW	106	2.03
CWC	112	2.05

For the collapse stress, the group CW increased by about 5.2% compared with the group C, and the CWC group increased by about 6.2% relative to the group C.

3. Numerical simulations

3. Numerical simulations

Typical load-displacement curve of test and simulation for group C(left), CW(middle), CWC(right)

Group	Young's modulus (MPa)	Collapse stress(MPa)
C-FEM	108	1.90
C-TEST	110	1.93
CW-FEM	111	2.02
CW-TEST	106	2.03
CWC-FEM	112	2.03
CWC-TEST	112	2.05

From the left table, simulation results are consistent with experimental results. The modulus of CW(FEM) and CWC (FEM) was close, both increased by about 2.7-3.7% relative to the modulus of the group C (FEM). The compressive strength was also close, which was about 6.3% higher than that of the group C (FEM).

4. PARAMETRIC SIMULATIONS

4.1 dislocation level

Top view of CW

Top view of CWC-1/4

Top view of CWC

A low level of dislocation leads to a decrease in the compressive performance of the core. This may be because the misalignment type of the CWC enables the two layers of honeycomb corners to support each other for better compression resistance.

Group	Young's modulus (MPa)	Collapse stress(MPa)
CW-FEM	111	2.02
CWC-FEM	112	2.03
CWC-1/4-FEM	112	1.91

From the data of the group CWC-1/4 that the modulus is almost unchanged with respect to the group CW, the collapse stress was decreased by 5.4%. It means dislocation type of CWC-1/4 has a negative effect on compression property.

4. PARAMETRIC SIMULATIONS

4.2 layers of honeycomb

Group	Young's modulus (MPa)	Collapse stress(MPa)
C-FEM	108	1.90
CW-FEM	111	2.02
CW3-FEM	112	2.03
CW4-FEM	116	2.17

The four-layer honeycomb has obvious performance enhancement. The modulus increases by 7.4% compared with the group C, and the collapse stress increases by 14.2%.

It shows that lower single height honeycomb is not prone to buckling, supply higher compressive strength.

4. PARAMETRIC SIMULATIONS

4.3 honeycomb height

CW(10+10)

CW(12.5+7.5)

CW(15+5)

Group	Young's modulus (MPa)	Collapse stress(MPa)
CW(10+10)-FEM	111	2.02
CW(12.5+7.5)-FEM	112	1.97
CW(15+5)-FEM	111	1.87

when the height of the honeycomb is different, the collapse stress of the honeycomb is decreased relative to the same height, and when the height difference between the two honeycombs increased, the performance degradation is more obvious

4. PARAMETRIC SIMULATIONS

4.4 height and dislocation of honeycomb

Compared to 4.3, dislocation has been added to the model, referred as CWC, in the case of different honeycomb heights, the dislocation can cause an increase in compression performance, which is more pronounced when the honeycomb height difference was obvious.

Group	Young's modulus (MPa)	Collapse stress(MPa)
CW(10+10)-FEM	111	2.02
CWC(10+10)-FEM	112	2.03
CW(7.5+12.5)-FEM	112	1.97
CWC(7.5+12.5)-FEM	113	1.98
CW(15+5)-FEM	111	1.87
CWC(15+5)-FEM	112	2.05

Top view of dislocation

This phenomenon means that the dislocation and the height of the honeycomb has the opposite effect.

5. CONCLUSION

1. The collapse stress of tandem honeycomb can be increased by more than 5% compared to single honeycomb. The desired functional layer (such as wave absorbing micro-structure layer) can be added between the honeycomb layers.
2. Dislocation type of corner align like CWC hardly affected in same height double layer, but the effect of dislocation on collapse stress is positive from the research of height.
3. In the case where the height of the core was determined, increasing the layer number of the tandem honeycombs could improve the compression resistance of the core. This proves that the low height honeycomb is not prone to buckling.
4. For double-layer tandem honeycombs, the inconsistent height of the single honeycomb has a negative impact on compression resistance of the core, this phenomenon indicates that the double-layer honeycomb collapse stress is dominated by the larger honeycomb, and the honeycomb height is more prone to buckling, resulting in lower collapse stress.